

**ALGORITHM FOR CREATING A WEB PLATFORM FOR THE
INDEPENDENT LEARNING ACTIVITIES OF STUDENTS OF THE
ACADEMIC LYCEUMS OF THE MINISTRY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS**

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Annotation. This article presents proposals and recommendations on the algorithm for creating and implementing a web platform designed to organize the independent learning activities of students of the academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs.

Keywords: students of the academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, independent learning activities, web platform, algorithm of creation and implementation.

At present, digital technologies are fundamentally renewing the educational process and creating wide opportunities for the effective organization of students' independent learning activities. In particular, in the academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the necessity of using modern web resources is increasing in deepening students' theoretical knowledge, forming their professional-social competence, and strengthening their self-development skills [1–2].

In recent years, many scientific studies have been conducted on the effectiveness of using digital learning resources and web platforms in the education system. In this regard, scientific research works have been carried out in our country, in the Commonwealth of Independent States and abroad by such scholars as N.I. Taylakov, U.M. Mirsanov, F.J. Toxirov, J.A. Elmurodov, N.N. Belseva, Z.Yu. Kutuzova, D.Yu. Ratushnyak, N. Barajas-Murphy, J. Wang, J.A. Leaston.

However, in the works of the scholars mentioned above, the issue of creating special platforms adapted to the independent learning activities of students in the academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs has not been sufficiently studied. Therefore, it is necessary to develop an algorithmic approach that ensures forming students as active subjects in the learning process, developing independent working skills, and personalizing the educational process. For this reason, on the basis of the analysis of the research of scholars in the field and our scientific investigations, an algorithm for creating and implementing a web platform for the independent learning activities of students of the academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs was developed

(see Figure 1). In developing this algorithm, the studies of U.M. Mirsanov [3], F.J. Toxirov [4] and J.A. Elmurodov [5] were used.

Figure 1. The algorithm for the design and implementation of a web platform to support independent learning activities of students in the academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs

Based on the algorithm illustrated in Figure 1, a web platform was developed for the independent learning activities of students of the academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs in the subjects “Physics” and “Informatics and Information Technologies.”

In conclusion, it can be said that the proposed algorithm integrates the technical, functional, and pedagogical aspects of the web platform, providing the opportunity to increase the level of mastery of students of the academic lyceums of the Ministry of

Internal Affairs, to develop independent working skills, and to personalize the educational process.

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